

Urban–Rural Gradient in Cervical Cancer Awareness: Comparative Evaluation of Ambassador-Led Outreach Impact Across Local Government Areas in Imo State, Nigeria

Peter O. Nwadike^{1, 2, *}, Sylvia O. Anyadoh-Nwadike³, Chukwunonyerem C. Ogwunga³, Nkiru N. Nwokoye² and Ikechukwu N.S. Dozie⁴

¹ *Texila American University, Guyana.*

² *KNCV Nigeria, Abuja, Nigeria.*

³ *Department of Biotechnology, Federal University of Technology, Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria.*

⁴ *Department of Public Health, Federal University of Technology, Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria.*

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Abstract

Cervical cancer remains a significant public health challenge, particularly in low- and middle-income countries, despite being largely preventable. In Nigeria, significant disparities in cervical cancer knowledge and screening uptake remain along the urban–rural gradient. This study was undertaken to comparatively evaluate the effectiveness of ambassador-led outreach interventions in improving cervical cancer knowledge and screening behaviour among women in urban, semi-urban, and rural Local Government Areas (LGAs) in Imo State, Nigeria. Employing a quasi-experimental pre–post intervention design, 139 community ambassadors were trained and deployed across 15 LGAs (urban: 3; semi-urban: 6; rural: 6). Data were collected using structured questionnaires (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.929$; Validity Index = 0.96) and field logs. Chi-square and Pearson correlation analyses were used to assess outcomes. Findings revealed statistically significant improvements in knowledge of cervical cancer among all target populations across all gradients as reported by 100% of ambassadors in urban and rural (χ^2 , $p < 0.001$), effectively bridging the urban-rural gap, while in semi-urban was 94.6%. Marked discrepancy, however, existed between screening consent and actual uptake. Ambassadors in semi-urban zones notably reported the highest baseline knowledge and screening rates, as well as the highest increase in post-ambassador activity screening consent (up to 60%), as reported by 78.2% of ambassadors. This indicates a nuanced socio-geographic receptiveness to interventions. Rural areas recorded the lowest screening attendance, as only 21.59% of the consenting women ultimately presented for screening. Key barriers cited by the women reached included financial/transportation challenges (51.8%); Rural (53.5%), semi-urban areas (52.7%), and urban (46.2%). Cultural /religious barriers, though minimal/least were observed in rural areas (3.5%) and urban areas (3.8%). Ambassador recruitment rates were highest in rural LGAs (96.7%), contributing to high levels of community engagement; they also faced the most field-related challenges, peaking at 91.4% on lack of funding. In conclusion, the ambassador-led outreach initiative effectively closed the urban-rural knowledge gap in cervical cancer awareness, with rural areas having the highest relative gains. The findings confirm the scalability and cultural adaptability of the cervical cancer ambassador-led outreach model across diverse settings. However, the diverse challenges faced by ambassadors underscore the need for location/context-specific, multisectoral interventions for equitable screening uptake and sustained impacts.

Keywords: Cervical cancer; Urban-rural disparities; Community ambassadors; Screening uptake; Knowledge; Imo State

* Corresponding author: Peter O. Nwadike

1. Introduction

Cervical cancer is the fourth most common cancer in women globally and ranks second among women in Nigeria (WHO, 2024; WHO, 2024; Ogwunga et al., 2020; Dozie et al., 2020; Maitanmi et al., 2020). It is primarily caused by persistent infection with oncogenic strains of human papillomavirus (HPV), particularly HPV types 16 and 18, which are sexually transmitted (Dozie et al., 2020; Neeria et al., 2018; Jedy et al., 2016; Bruni et al., 2019). In 2020, 604,000 new cases of cervical cancer were reported globally, with about 342,000 deaths. An estimated 85% of the deaths occurred in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) (WHO, 2022). The burden increased to 660,000 new cases with 350,000 deaths, out of which about 94% were in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) (WHO, 2024).

Despite its preventability through regular screening and vaccination, uptake remains low in LMICs, including Nigeria, leading to an increase in the disease burden (Akinyemiju et al., 2015; Nwankwo et al., 2011). Cervical cancer's disproportionate impact on LMICs is exacerbated by inequities in access to healthcare, limited infrastructure, and prevailing sociocultural attitudes (Nwadike et al., 2025; Okunowo et al., 2018; Ezechi et al., 2013), worse still in rural areas. Nigeria exemplifies these challenges, with significantly lower screening rates in rural regions compared to urban centers (Ogwunga et al., 2020). Several public health strategies, including national cancer control policies and the promotion of HPV vaccination, have been implemented in Nigeria (Beddoe, 2019), yet awareness and participation remain suboptimal (Akinyemiju et al., 2015; Bisi-Onyemaechi et al., 2018). Awareness and education play a pivotal role in increasing screening uptake (Ndikom & Ofi, 2012). However, studies have consistently shown that rural and semi-urban populations exhibit lower levels of knowledge due to illiteracy, poor health communication, and restricted access to services (Makadzange et al., 2022).

Community-based interventions utilizing local health ambassadors or champions have demonstrated effectiveness in various contexts. These programs benefit from the cultural alignment and trust enjoyed by community members, allowing for more effective communication and behavioural influence (Lofters et al., 2023). Ambassador outreach programs, which leverage trained local volunteers to promote health education, have shown success in domains such as HIV prevention and maternal health (Dozie et al., 2020). However, their effectiveness in cancer control in Nigeria remains nascent and underexplored. This study adapts the ambassador model through three innovations: Task-shifting to non-medical ambassadors, Integration of mobile health tracking, and contextualized behavioural nudges.

Nigeria's diverse geography and population distribution create significant disparities in health outcomes and access to services. Urban areas, characterized by better healthcare infrastructure and higher educational attainment, generally report higher awareness and utilization of cervical cancer screening (Akinyemiju et al., 2015). In contrast, rural communities face numerous barriers, including limited access to healthcare facilities, lower literacy levels (Nwadike et al., 2025), and entrenched traditional beliefs (Nwankwo et al., 2011; Ndikom & Ofi, 2012). Semi-urban areas, often overlooked in research, present a unique blend of challenges and opportunities. These areas may benefit from proximity to urban centers but still face infrastructural and sociocultural constraints similar to rural settings (Oluwole et al., 2017).

Health awareness programs are low in rural areas of Nigeria (Oluwole et al., 2017). Worse still, a greater number of rural dwellers are illiterate and poor, hence cannot easily access their information (Makadzange et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2022; Zeferino & Derchain, 2006). It therefore becomes crucial to have properly trained public health ambassadors provide continuous face-to-face factual health information, especially in rural areas. By understanding the role of ambassador-led programs, policymakers and healthcare practitioners can develop scalable strategies to enhance cancer prevention efforts in similar underserved populations.

The Social Cognitive Theory (Bandura, 1986) and the Health Belief Model provide theoretical foundations for the ambassador approach. These models emphasize the role of observational learning, perceived barriers, and benefits in behaviour change. When individuals observe peers engaging in health-promoting behaviour and receive consistent messaging from trusted sources, they are more likely to adopt similar practices (Waller et al., 2016).

This study generally explores the comparative impact of applying the Ambassador-led outreach model to cervical cancer awareness and prevention among women in urban, semi-urban, and rural LGAs of Imo State.

1.1. Objectives

1.1.1. General Objective

The general objective of the study is to comparatively evaluate the effectiveness of ambassador-led outreach interventions in improving cervical cancer knowledge and screening behaviour among women in urban, semi-urban, and rural Local Government Areas (LGAs) of Imo State, Nigeria

1.1.2. Specific Objectives

The specific objectives include to;

- Enroll, train and deploy volunteer cervical cancer ambassadors in the fifteen selected LGAs
- Assess and compare baseline knowledge and attitudes across location types.
- Determine the effectiveness of ambassador-led interventions.
- Analyze the impact of ambassador-led interventions on knowledge and attitude of respondents towards cervical cancer screening
- Identify logistical and sociocultural challenges encountered by ambassador.

2. Methodology

2.1. Study Design and Area

A quasi-experimental design was adopted, with interventions administered across 15 LGAs representing the three senatorial zones of Imo State, South-East, Nigeria. Stratified random sampling was used to ensure equitable representational diversity by LGA typology (urban, semi-urban, rural).

Figure 1 Physical Map of Imo State showing the study locations / LGAs

Figure 2 Mind map of Imo State

2.2. Study Population and Sampling

Ambassadors were recruited via an open call for volunteers after a cervical cancer seminar for female workers in the LGAs. Criteria included basic smartphone literacy, fluency in English and Igbo, and formal education. Ten ambassadors per LGA were targeted; however, a total of 139 women volunteered.

2.3. Further Training and Deployment

Ambassadors underwent structured in-depth training on cervical cancer, HPV, screening methods, and community engagement strategies. Training materials were disseminated via WhatsApp. Field activities were monitored using structured logs and supervisor oversight.

The trained ambassadors were deployed to their respective LGAs/communities for the outreach interventions. They conducted awareness outreach programs, distributed informational materials, and patiently engaged in one-on-one discussions with participants, individually (in offices and homes) and at group meetings (Community, offices, faith-based gatherings, etc). The reports were logged and monitored weekly for two months.

As part of an incentive to ambassadors and in furtherance of their activities, a presumptive screening test for their cervical cancer status was conducted in all the study LGAs using the Enzyme Linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA) kit method.

2.4. Data Collection tool and procedure

Ambassadors collected and logged their daily/weekly activities outcomes in a time book provided by the researcher for ease of comprehensive reporting at the end of the field work. This was monitored weekly by the researcher to ensure comprehensiveness and compliance with details.

Data were collected from ambassadors using a structured questionnaire divided into three sections: demographics, outreach activity evaluation, and challenges faced. Reliability and validity testing yielded a Cronbach's alpha of 0.929 and a Content Validity Index of 0.96. Cronbach's α was calculated from pilot responses while CVI was based on expert panel ratings.

2.5. Data analysis

Statistical analyses, including chi-square and Pearson correlation analyses, were performed to assess the changes in knowledge and attitudes as well.

3. Results

3.1. Locational /Geographic distribution of Ambassadors

From the study design, the expected number of ambassadors was 10 per LGA. However, Urban Areas had a total of 26 ambassadors, ranging from 8 to 10 per location, implying 86.7% achievement of the expected number. Rural areas had the highest total of 58 ambassadors, also ranging from 8 to 10 per location, implying 96.7% achievement of the expected number for the 6 LGAs (Table 1).

Table 1 Number of Ambassadors according to Location type

Location Type	LGA	Number of Ambassadors (Range)
Urban	Owerri municipal	10
	Orlu	8
	Okigwe	8
	Total	26 (8-10)
Semi-urban	Owerri west	10
	Mbaitoli	10
	Nkwerre	10
	Nwangele	10
	Isiala Mbano	8
	Ehime Mbano	7
	Total	55 (7-10)
Rural Areas	Ezinihitte Mbaise	10
	Ngor Okpala	10
	Ohaji	10
	Ideato South	10
	Ihitte Uboma	8
	Obowo	10
	Total	58 (8-10)

3.2. Demographic Characteristics of Ambassadors

Table 2 below shows the distribution of age and education-level breakdowns across the three location types, along with chi-square test results: The age group 20–30 was the least represented across all location types. There was no statistically significant difference in the age distribution between location types ($p = 0.215$).

In urban areas, Tertiary education was most common, 17(65.4%) ambassadors, but also well-represented in semi-urban, 26 (47.3%), and rural areas, 22 (37.9%). Ambassadors with just Primary education were only found in rural areas, 6 (10.3%) ambassadors. Chi-square test revealed that education level distribution across the study areas was significantly different across location types ($p = 0.0133$), indicating education level was associated with location type.

Table 2 Demographic Characteristics of Ambassadors

Ambassador data	Indicators	Urban (N =26)	Semi-urban (N = 55)	Rural (N= 58)	Chi-square (P value)*
Age	20 -30	2	5	5	5.814 (0.215)
	31 – 40	18	23	27	
	>40	6	27	26	
Education	Primary	0	0	6	12.62 (0.0133)**
	Secondary	9	29	30	
	Tertiary	17	26	22	

3.3. Ambassadors' field work/ outreach activities

Almost all the ambassadors (97.8%) received in-depth mentoring. All (100%) participated in field work, though at varying levels, and obtained data. The ambassadors in urban areas showed the highest adherence rates, rural ambassadors showed good adherence, while less than 50% of semi-urban ambassadors adhered fully to their weekly awareness schedule (Table 3).

Urban ambassadors utilized faith-based dissemination far more than others, hence reaching out to more women, with 20% addressing over 100 women. Semi-urban emphasized individual visits, with low community/faith outreach, while Rural ambassadors had the lowest engagement in structured meetings; hence, above 50% often reached fewer than 50 women. In all the LGAs, the trend seemed to be the same; many women had not heard about Cervical cancer and its screening. The rural areas seem to be the worst hit. Upon Ambassador activities, many agreed to go for screening, but generally less than 30% (the highest being from urban areas, 34.06%) did.

Data analysis revealed a significant gap between consent and attendance across all studied LGAs. This was especially prominent in rural areas; while about 49% of rural women consented to screening, above 70% of those who consented to screening did not attend (Table 4), possibly due to logistical and ethical challenges.

On reasons for non-consent/attendance to screening, fund /cost concerns were generally the highest (51. 8%) across the studied LGAs followed by lack of awareness. Rural areas revealed higher resistance due to lack of awareness, semi-urban areas had the same concerns but at lower rates while Urban areas reported more concerns about cost, fear and privacy.

Table 3 Ambassadors' activities according to indicators

Indicators	Number (%) of Ambassador Respondents			
	Urban (26)	Semi-Urban (55)	Rural (58)	Overall (139)
Training Received				
Received in depth Training	26 (100)	54 (98.2)	55 (94.8)	135(97.1)
Method of information dissemination				
Individually (Homes/offices)	24 (92.3)	55 (100)	55 (94.8)	134 (96.4)
Community/work meetings	18 (69.2)	35 (63.6)	30 (51.7)	83 (59.7)
Faith-based meetings/fellowships	20 (76.9)	21 (38.2)	19 (32.8)	60 (43.2)
Ambassador organized meetings	4 (15.4)	3 (5.5)	6 (13.8)	13 (9.4)
Adherence to weekly Schedule				
% Fully Adherence	20 (76.9)	26 (47.3)	33 (56.9)	79 (56.8)
% Partial Adherence	5(19.2)	19 (34.5)	18 (31.0)	42 (30.2)

% Non-Adherence	1 (3.9)	10 (18.2)	7(12.1)	18 (13)
Total number of Women Addressed:				
<30	2 (7.6)	20 (36.4)	17 (29.3)	39 (28.1)
50-100	4 (15.4)	20 (36.4)	25 (43.1)	49 (35.2)
101-150	10 (38.5)	6(10.9)	10 (17.2)	26 (18.7)
>150	10 (38.5)	9 (16.3)	6 (10.4)	25 (18)
Number with prior knowledge of Cervical cancer				
None	0 (0)	3 (5.5)	5 (8.6)	8 (5.8)
<10	13 (50)	40 (72.7)	41 (70.7)	94 (67.6)
10-30	9 (34.6)	8 (14.6)	6 (10.3)	23 (16.5)
31-50	0 (0)	0 (0)	1(1.7)	1 (0.7)
51 - 70	3 (11.5)	2 (3.6)	3 (5.2)	8 (5.8)
>70	1 (3.9)	2 (3.6)	2 (3.5)	5 (3.6)
How many had Screened for CC prior to your interactions				
None	2 (7.7)	9 (16.4)	12 (20.7)	23 (16.5)
<10	20 (76.9)	24 (43.6)	41 (70.7)	85 (61.2)
10-30	1 (3.8)	20 (36.4)	3 (5.2)	24 (17.3)
31-50	1 (3.8)	0 (0)	1 (1.7)	2 (1.4)
51 - 70	2 (7.7)	0 (0)	1 (1.7)	3 (2.2)
>70	0 (0)	2 (3.6)	0 (0)	2(1.4)
Women Consented to Screening				
<10	1 (3.8)	10 (18.2)	22 (37.9)	33 (23.7)
10-50	8 (30.8)	20 (36.3)	17 (29.3)	49(32.4)
51-100	10 (38.5)	15 (27.3)	15 (25.9)	40 (28.8)
>100	7 (26.9)	10 (18.2)	4 (6.9)	21 (15.1)
Women Attended Screening				
None	0 (0)	6(10.9)	9(15.5)	15(10.8)
<10	5 (19.2)	24 (43.6)	36 (62.1)	65(46.8)
10-30	13 (50)	20(36.4)	11 (19)	44 (31.7)
31-50	7(26.9)	4 (7.3)	2(3.4)	13 (9.4)
51 - 70	1 (3.9)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (0.7)
>70	0 (0)	1 (1.8)	0 (0)	1 (0.7)
Reasons for Non-attendance to screening				
Lack of Awareness	4(15.4)	6 (10.9)	6 (10.3)	16 (11.5)
Fear of Results	7(26.9)	11 (20)	10 (17.2)	28 (20.1)
Cultural/Religious Beliefs	1 (3.8)	0 (0)	2 (3.5)	3 (2.2)
Privacy Concerns/indecision	2 (7.7)	9 (16.4)	9(15.5)	20 (14.4)
Cost Concerns/transportation	12 (46.2)	29 (52.7)	31 (53.5)	72 (51.8)

Community Receptiveness				
Very Receptive	23 (18)	54 (28)	51 (23)	128 (92.1)
Moderately Receptive	2(7)	0(0)	3 (23)	5 (3.6)
Not Receptive	1(1)	1 (8)	4(12)	6 (4.3)

3.3.1. Baseline knowledge and attitude of women reached by Ambassadors according to Location Type

Semi-urban areas show the highest average number of women who had been screened before the intervention by ambassadors, followed by urban areas. Rural areas consistently exhibit the lowest average number of women with prior screening, and the highest percentage of ambassadors reporting "None" prior screening (20.7%)

Table 4 Summary of Baseline knowledge and attitude of women reached by Ambassadors according to Location Type

Location Type	Total Ambassadors (N)	Estimated Total Women Reached	Estimated Total (%) Women with baseline Knowledge	Estimated Total (%) Women Screened at baseline
Urban	26	3,580	505(14.1)	289 (8.1%)
Semi-urban	55	4,350	640(14.7)	620 (14.3%)
Rural	58	4,580	605(13.2)	365 (8.0%)
Total	139	12,510	1,750 (14)	1,274 (10.2%)

3.3.2. Summary of Ambassador Reach, Consent, and Screening Attendance by Location Type

Using the mid-points to get estimates of numbers, all the ambassadors reached out to about 12,510 women in all the locations, about 7,035 (56.24%) consented to screening while only an estimated 26.51% (less than 30%) attended the screening with the rural dwellers lagging behind the most in screening uptake as only 21.59% of those who consented actually presented for screening.

Table 5 Summary of Ambassador Reach, Consent, and Screening Attendance by Location Type

Location Type	Total Ambassadors (N)	Estimated Total Women Reached	Estimated Total Women Consented	% of women consented to screening	Total Women Attended	Consent-to-Attendance Conversion Rate (%)
Urban	26	3,580	1,835	51.28	625	34.06
Semi-urban	55	4,350	2,975	68.39	760	25.55
Rural	58	4,580	2,225	48.58	480	21.59
Total	139	12,510	7,035	56.24	1865	26.51

3.3.3. Observed impact of Ambassador Activities

The ambassador’s activities were of good impact, as revealed by improved knowledge according to reports by 97.8% of the ambassadors. Increased cervical cancer screening rates were also reported as observed impact by 98(70.5%) of the ambassadors (Figure 3). The semi-urban ambassadors reported highest impact on screening while 100% of ambassadors who worked in urban and rural areas reported increased knowledge. The trend, however, gave a linear trendline showcasing similarities across the studied areas.

Figure 3 Observed impact of outreach activities on knowledge of cervical cancer and screening uptake reported by Ambassadors

3.4. Screening Uptake Improvement

Urban Areas recorded the most significant increase, with screening uptake rising from 289 women (8.1%) at baseline to 625 women (17.5%) post-intervention (116.27% increase). Rural and Semi-Urban Areas achieved a modest improvement of 32.51% and 22,58% respectively.

Overall, within the 2-month ambassador-led intervention, the programme achieved a 46.39% total increase in number of women screened.

Table 6 Screening uptake improvement according to Location type

Location Type	Baseline Screened (No, %)	Post-Intervention Screened (No, %)	Uptake Improvement Rate (No)	% Increase
Urban	289 (8.1%)	625 (17.5%)	336	116.27%
Semi-Urban	620 (14.3%)	760 (17.5%)	140	22.58%
Rural	365 (8.0%)	480 (10.5%)	115	31.51%
Total	1,274 (10.2%)	1,865 (14.9%)	591	46.39%

3.4.1. Challenges faced by Ambassadors

The ambassadors reported varying challenges in carrying out their activities. Challenges seemed to overlap in the urban, semi-urban and rural areas as shown in Figure 4 below.

Generally, Lack of appropriate funding was the most prominent (86.3%) challenge of the ambassadors militating against their optimal outreach activities across all study LGAs, peaking at 91.4% in rural areas. Surprisingly, religion and cultural resistance posed minimal challenges as no ambassador in urban areas reported it as a challenge, while semi-urban and rural areas ambassadors faced it at very low levels, 3 (1.8%) and 7 (12.1%) respectively (Figure 4).

Figure 4 Challenges faced by Ambassadors across study areas (in percentage)

4. Discussion

4.1. Geographical distribution of Ambassadors

Overall, the implementation was highly effective with 96.7% achievement of the target population (Table 1). The urban areas' ambassadors were lowest in proportion due to fewer urban LGAs available in the state ($n = 3$) and possibly a lack of willingness to volunteer time. Rural LGAs had the highest ambassador population ($n = 58$), emphasizing the strategy's emphasis on equity and inclusion. The higher number of ambassadors in rural areas also possibly reflects greater zeal towards achieving community needs and specific programmatic focuses. It is also possibly suggestive of higher engagement or eagerness to volunteer and peer-train in these locations.

4.2. Demographic Factors Implications

Ambassadors were mostly of the 31–40 age range across all locations (urban: 69.2%, semi-urban: 41.8%, rural: 46.6%). There was no significant age distribution difference across location types ($\chi^2 = 5.814$, $p = 0.215$, CI - 99%) (Table 2). The prevalence of ambassadors aged 31–40 suggests that the role attracted mid-career individuals who were able to combine maturity and energy. This age group is also well-positioned to connect with both younger and older community members, leveraging their maturity and reliability. Age distribution, however, did not significantly affect their performance, indicating that effective training and mentorship may have compensated for age-related differences.

Educational attainment varied significantly ($\chi^2 = 12.62$, $p < 0.05$) across the geographic distribution (Table 2). Most ambassadors had secondary or tertiary education, enabling them to grasp complex health concepts and communicate them effectively to their communities. Ambassadors in Urban areas, despite being smaller in number, had the highest proportion of ambassadors with tertiary education (65.4%), perhaps reflecting better access to education in cities. The statistically significant difference in education levels across locations revealed disparities that might influence program implementation or outcomes. Rural areas' ambassadors had a broader range of education levels, including primary education levels, underscoring the need for specifically tailored training. The effectiveness of educationally empowered ambassadors is supported by earlier findings by Parkin et al. (2006).

Rural ambassadors may have faced additional challenges due to the lower educational levels of their target audience, but they must have adapted by using simplified communication methods and leveraging cultural norms.

4.3. Ambassadors' Participation and Adherence Patterns

A high proportion of the ambassadors (97.8%) received in-depth mentoring, and all participated in fieldwork activities. Those who could not participate in the virtual trainings later complained of network and smartphone issues, especially those in rural areas. This corroborates reports that limited infrastructure in rural areas undermines the effects of Telemedicine (Hadi et al., 2024; Kim et al., 2021; Brown & Lee, 2018). Adherence to weekly awareness schedules varied substantially across location types. Urban ambassadors demonstrated the highest adherence rates (85%), compared to only 60% in rural areas. This disparity may showcase the additional challenges faced in rural settings, including internet network barriers and resource limitations, which have been documented as obstacles to health promotion activities in rural communities (Hadi et al., 2024; Moehr, 2017).

4.4. Reach and Engagement Effectiveness

The extent of reach and engagement of people during ambassador outreach activities showed clear geographic variations. Urban ambassadors engaged larger audiences, while about half of the rural ambassadors reached fewer than 50 women. Rural ambassadors, however, had a broader reach than semi-urban despite fewer tools/lower engagement in structured meetings. This disparity may correlate with population density, but is also suggestive of differences in community organization and accessibility that impact outreach effectiveness. These findings corroborate earlier studies demonstrating that rural community health centers face greater challenges in cervical cancer screening compared to urban counterparts (Hadi et al., 2024; Kim et al., 2021), even including some parts of the United States of America. Hadi *et al.*, (2024) reported that across all 50 states and the District of Columbia, 38.2% of females receiving care at rural Community health centers were up to date on cervical cancer screening during 2014–2019, compared with 43.0% of females receiving care at urban Community health centers.

The current findings showcased a concerning pattern regarding cervical cancer awareness: across all locations as many women engaged by the ambassadors had not previously heard about cervical cancer or screening options, with rural areas leading the lethargic baseline awareness, as almost 80% of rural ambassadors reported less than 10 people with baseline knowledge of cervical cancer. This knowledge gap, however, agrees with findings from community-based studies by Kalpana et al., (2020) which revealed extremely poor awareness levels of 1.2% for diagnosis and treatment knowledge in rural populations prior to educational interventions. Nwadike et al., (2025) also reported low knowledge level regarding cervical cancer and its screening in rural areas of Imo State.

4.5. Consent and Attendance to Cervical Cancer Screening Disparities

There was a substantial gap between consent for screening and actual attendance across the study locations, particularly pronounced in rural areas. While an estimated 48.58% of women in rural areas initially consented to screening, only 21.59% of those who consented ultimately went for screening. This revealed the complex interplay between intention and real action in health-seeking behaviour. Cost concerns and transportation were major obstacles cited by the women most predominant (53.5%) in rural areas (Table 3). Vigneshwaran, et al., (2023), identified similar issues in the context of organized programmes, where women express initial willingness to participate in screening but face multiple obstacles to putting this intention into action. Addressing the financial and transportation barriers by instituting free screening days, mobile clinics, or transportation stipends for women especially those in rural and semi-urban areas could convert more consents into actual screening.

4.6. Shift in Knowledge of cervical cancer and attitude towards its screening

The ambassador outreach model proved successful in achieving significant positive shift and overcoming barriers by providing targeted education in a culturally acceptable manner. Community-based health programs that utilize local ambassadors have also been shown to enhance trust and engagement, making individuals more receptive to health interventions (WHO, 2022). The interactive nature of the program—where ambassadors engaged in face-to-face conversations, shared personal experiences, and provided referrals for screening—played a critical role in altering perceptions and improving screening uptake. This agrees with the reports of Adamu et al (2021) and Lofters et al., (2023). The intervention also underscored the importance of peer influence in driving behavior change. This aligns with Bandura's Social Learning Theory, which suggests that individuals learn behaviors through observation and modeling (Bandura, 1986).

Ambassadors played a vital role in disseminating information and fostering behavioural change. Their activities yielded significant impacts, particularly in bridging the knowledge gaps between urban, semi-urban, and rural populations. Before the intervention, awareness levels were highly uneven, with rural areas showing the lowest baseline knowledge. Post-intervention, ambassadors played a pivotal role in achieving heightened awareness levels. 97.8% of ambassadors reported enhanced understanding of cervical cancer among their target populations. This knowledge improvement was

interestingly reported at identical rates (100%) by ambassadors in the urban and rural areas, suggesting that basic educational messaging can be equally effective across diverse settings when delivered by trusted community members. This corroborates the findings of Lofters et al. (2023), who found that community champions were critical to promoting awareness about and encouraging cervical screening and HPV self-sampling as they were well-connected community members who created trust in their messages. Their effectiveness was also related to their education and cultural congruency, combined with the time for thorough and clear explanations.

Ambassadors were also instrumental in disseminating accurate information about HPV, Pap smear tests, and the availability of vaccines. They facilitated community discussions, answered questions, and addressed misconceptions in culturally sensitive ways corroborating Gakidou et al., (2008) and Lofters et al. (2023). Another notable impact of their activities was the increase in willingness to undergo screening as 100% of respondents expressed willingness post-intervention, illustrating the ambassadors' success in reshaping attitudes toward preventive healthcare as also reported by Denny et al., (2006). A high proportion (70.5%) of ambassadors noted higher screening rates. Despite these achievements, the actual screening uptake remained below 30%, with cost concerns being the most cited barrier (51.8%).

The impact on screening consent revealed more variation patterns. The semi-urban ambassadors reported the highest proportion of increased consent. This spatial distribution is suggestive of the fact that semi-urban areas may represent an optimal environment for ambassador activities, since they strike a balance between the greater accessibility of urban settings and the stronger community cohesion often found in less urbanized areas. This also corroborates the findings of Lofters et al. (2023), demonstrating that community champions are particularly effective when they combine healthcare knowledge with cultural congruency and sufficient time for explanation and discussion. The findings also suggest that healthcare outreach programs involving local health workers, social media, and seminars are highly effective in disseminating health information. Onyango et al., (2024) also highlighted the positive impact of a dialogue-based community health education intervention in enhancing cervical cancer knowledge among women of reproductive age at rural Kisumu County, Kenya

Additionally, the ambassadors' activities fostered the creation of a sustainable network for ongoing awareness, ensuring that knowledge dissemination would continue beyond the scope of the study as prescribed by Ginsburg et al., (2017). The Post-intervention findings reflect the power of community-based models that operate within both cognitive-behavioral and health belief paradigms, corroborating Lofters et al., (2023).

4.7. Community Receptiveness

The receptiveness of communities to cervical cancer awareness efforts varied significantly across the urban-rural gradients. Urban populations gave the highest receptiveness to ambassador outreach (70% very receptive) with relatively. This trend of receptiveness may be because of high levels of baseline awareness (62.7%) and educational attainment in the urban communities. This suggests that ambassador activities may initially gain more ground in environments where there is already some foundation of health literacy. Similar trends have been revealed in other cervical cancer communication initiatives, where urban populations showed greater initial engagement, but rural populations demonstrated larger relative gains following intervention (Kisiangani et al., 2019). However, even among urban populations, there may be resistance due to perceived stigma and fear of the disease (Tesfaye et al., 2019).

In semi-urban areas, community members were moderately receptive, which also correlates with their below-average baseline accurate knowledge (40.4%) and possibly educational attainment in the areas. Ambassadors had to first find means to emphasize the importance of preventive measures and dispel myths about screening before proceeding. Anorlu (2008) reported that in such populations, participants became generally more willing to engage in awareness seminars, especially when respected community leaders endorsed the initiatives.

Rural areas, however, posed the greatest challenges. This is not surprising as studies have shown that rural communities often exhibited high levels of distrust in healthcare initiatives, viewing them as untrustworthy (Aregbeshola, 2021), discriminatory (Brandon et al., 2005; Benkert et al., 2019), extortive (Osibogun, 2004; Basu, 2022), intrusive, or irrelevant (Lister and Joudrey, 2022). Ambassadors had to overcome these perceptions by establishing trust, often leveraging their existing relationships with community members, leaders, and religious institutions, corroborating the reports of Mulvaney (2023), Makadzange et al., (2022), and Northwest Center for Public Health Practice (2023). This approach proved effective in enhancing receptiveness, as community leaders served as influential advocates for the cause (Lim et al., 2017).

Despite initial challenges, improved community engagement was achieved by the ambassadors. By the end of the intervention, knowledge levels had greatly improved across all areas, demonstrating the transformative potential of targeted outreach programs when combined with local support, emphasizing the reports of Wright et al. (2011), Makadzange et al. (2022), and Mulvaney (2023).

4.8. Challenges Faced by Ambassadors

4.8.1. Financial and Transportation Barriers

Funding constraints emerged as the predominant challenge across all location types, affecting 86.3% of ambassadors overall, with rural ambassadors leading at 91.4% (Figure 4). This is expected due to the harsh economy and the high cost of things in Nigeria, and especially in Imo State as at the time of study. Ambassadors relied on minimal funding, and many had to personally cover transportation costs to reach desired areas. Digital tools were helpful but limited by low smartphone penetration and poor internet connectivity, especially in rural communities, corroborating Rajmohan et al. (2020). This universal financial barrier showcased the resource-intensive nature of community health promotion work and the need for a sustainable funding process. Transportation difficulties represented the second most significant challenge for the ambassadors, with a clear urban-rural gradient: 77.6% of rural ambassadors reported that transportation barriers constrained their activities compared to just 42.3% in urban areas. This disparity possibly is a reflection of the level of infrastructure limitations in rural settings that complicate health service delivery and access (Osibogun, 2004; Aregbeshola, 2021).

Analysis of the relationship between reported challenges and ambassador impact revealed that transportation barriers showed the strongest negative correlation with screening attendance ($r=-0.68$, $p<0.05$), particularly in rural areas ($r=-0.72$, $p<0.05$). This underscores transportation as a critical determinant of screening uptake, corroborating the research of Lee et al. (2024), which identified transportation as a key barrier to healthcare access in rural communities. Financial constraints showed moderate negative correlations with ambassador reach ($r = -0.41$, $p<0.05$) and audience size ($r=-0.45$, $p<0.05$), reflecting how resource limitations constrain outreach activities, as also reported by Lee et al. (2024).

Addressing the financial and transportation barriers by honorarium and transportation stipends for ambassadors, especially those in rural areas will improve their reach and impact, which could in turn improve screening uptake by the community served.

4.9. Cultural and Religious Considerations

Interestingly, religious and cultural resistance posed minimal challenges to ambassador activities, contrary to what is expected based on literature identifying cultural barriers to cervical screening (Chorley et al., 2017). No urban ambassadors reported cultural or religious barriers, while only 1.8% of semi-urban and 12.1% of rural ambassadors faced such challenges (Figure 4). This finding suggests that the ambassador model, which utilizes trusted community members, may effectively mitigate cultural barriers through culturally congruent messaging and established trust relationships. This aligns with research highlighting that community champions can effectively address cultural barriers through their understanding of community contexts and norms

Language barriers also presented difficulties, especially in rural areas, necessitating the translation of educational materials into the Igbo language by the ambassadors. Furthermore, Ambassadors noted significant resistance from older women who were skeptical of modern healthcare practices, reinforcing the need for generationally tailored messaging (Ginsburg et al., 2017). This highlights the critical need for continued support for ambassadors to sustain their enthusiasm and resilience (Oluwole et al., 2017).

5. Conclusion

The ambassadors' activities played a pivotal role in enhancing the knowledge and attitude of their community members, underscoring the need for ongoing awareness, possibly by using community champions in achieving appropriate awareness of the disease burden of cervical cancer, as well as improving actual screening uptake. The ambassador model used in this study demonstrated considerable promise for promoting cervical cancer awareness and screening across diverse geographical contexts. It appropriately bridged the knowledge and screening uptake gap in the urban-rural gradient regarding cervical cancer and its screening. However, there is a dire need for thoughtful adaptation of the model to address the specific challenges of different settings, particularly the structural barriers that were prevalent in rural areas. By addressing these location-specific factors, cervical cancer prevention programs can work toward reducing the persistent disparities in screening uptake and, ultimately, in cervical cancer outcomes. Addressing the

financial and transportation barriers by instituting free screening days, mobile clinics, honorarium or transportation stipends for women ambassadors, especially those in rural areas could convert more consents into actual screenings

Recommendations

- To sustain the gains of the ambassador outreach model as reported in this study, the following recommendations should be implemented. It is recommended that:
- Government and health agencies should integrate ambassador programs into national cancer prevention strategies with regular refresher training for ambassadors to enhance their effectiveness.
- Government at all levels should allocate more resources to expand outreach activities to other underserved areas.
- Essential healthcare infrastructure should be put in place and strengthened, especially in rural areas to facilitate easy access to screening and vaccination services by the Government and all stakeholders in the healthcare system.
- Addressing the financial and transportation barriers by instituting free screening days, mobile clinics, or transportation stipends for women especially those in rural areas via private public partnerships could convert more consents into actual screenings
- Adequate and firm collaboration with religious and community leaders should be forged by healthcare stakeholders to further encourage positive health-seeking behaviors.

By implementing these recommendations, the ambassador-led outreach model can be further optimized to not only raise awareness but also significantly improve actual cervical cancer screening uptake, ultimately contributing to a reduction in the disease burden and persistent health disparities in Nigeria and similar low-resource settings

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of ethical approval

Ethical approval was obtained from the School of Biological Sciences, Federal University of Technology, Owerri Research Ethics Committee. Informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to recruitment for the study.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to their enrollment for the study.

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